

CAPILLARY WICKING IN FLAX FIBER REINFORCEMENTS; ORTHOTROPIC ISSUES AND COMPARISON WITH CARBON REINFORCEMENTS

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ABSTRACT

During impregnation of a fibrous reinforcement in Liquid Composite Moulding (LCM) process, capillary effects have to be considered, in order to identify their influence on void formation in composite parts. Wicking in a fibrous medium described by Washburn equation was considered as equivalent to a flow under the effect of a capillary-pressure according to Darcy's law. Experimental tests for characterization of wicking in both flax and carbon fibers reinforcements were carried out in their three main directions for quasi-UD fabrics by means of a tensiometer. Then, through the equivalence between Washburn and Darcy laws, an "orthotropic capillary-pressure" was identified. However for flax fibers reinforcements, results of wicking tests are a superposition of different phenomena due to its sensitivity to humidity. In order to make fibers less sensitive to water sorption, a thermal treatment was carried out on flax reinforcements. Swelling tests proved that treated flax fibers are less sensitive to these effects and wicking has a similar trend to those found for carbon fabrics, allowing determination of capillary pressure.

1 INTRODUCTION

With the increased use of Liquid Composite Moulding (LCM) for composites manufacturing in the transportation industry, the complexity of part shapes and quality requirements have increased. Those effective and low cost processes are thus an interesting way to manufacture both high performance and bio-based composites. Void formation during LCM processes calls for an improved understanding of the impregnation local phenomenon and capillary pressure effects, in order to develop models for fibrous preforms filling and to achieve porosity location prediction in composite parts [1]. Some experimental [2-3] and numerical studies [4-5] have already shown the necessity of measuring physical parameters, such as "capillary pressure".

Moreover the need for more sustainable materials either biodegradable or fully recyclable has pushed the composite industry to look increasingly at bio-based reinforcements and resins, but avoiding some chemical treatments that could generate unhealthy products or wastes [6-7]. Flax reinforcements are a good alternative to some conventional reinforcements in terms of mechanical properties, but moisture sorption and worse interfacial adhesion with resin make still them less attractive [8].

Fibrous reinforcements are porous media, that can be idealised as a capillary tube network and thus wicking in media can be described by a modified Washburn equation [9]. In parallel, Darcy law describes liquid flow in a porous medium through a pressure gradient, related to average liquid velocity by material permeability and liquid viscosity [10]. Impregnation of reinforcements depends on flow direction, usually characterized in reference to the principal directions of the preform.

In this work we propose a new definition of capillary pressure through the equivalence of Washburn and Darcy laws with spontaneous wicking. Wicking tests were carried out by means of a tensiometer for quasi-UD carbon and flax fabrics. By a fit of experimental curves with Washburn equation, parameters taking into account geometry of porous medium and then interactions between liquid and reinforcement were identified for carbon fabrics. In first approach, the liquid used to set this new procedure was water. Once all parameters were determined, values of capillary pressure in each

direction were calculated. For flax fibers, fit of experimental wicking curves was not possible because of moisture sorption. Flax fabrics were then submitted to a thermal treatment that modifies the wetting behaviour of fibers [11]. Sensitivity to water sorption was evaluated through swelling tests on untreated and treated single fibers. After minimization of sensitivity to polar liquid sorption, wicking in flax fabrics shows trend similar to carbon fabrics.

2 THEORY

Wicking in a porous medium can be described by two approaches: modified Washburn equation and Darcy law. In this section both equations in the case of one-dimensional flow are discussed and, considering their equivalence, a new expression to determine capillary pressure is introduced.

2.1 Washburn equation

From equilibrium between viscous and capillary forces and neglecting gravity effects, Washburn equation [9] describing capillary rise of a liquid in a tube can be written as follow:

$$h^2(t) = \frac{r \gamma_L \cos \theta_a}{2 \eta} t \quad (1)$$

where h is the distance travelled by the liquid front, r the radius of the capillary tube, θ_a the advancing contact angle, η the viscosity of the liquid and t the time of flow (Fig.1-a). This equation as function of mass gain over time can be written:

$$m^2(t) = \frac{\pi^2 r^5 \rho^2 \gamma_L \cos \theta_a}{2 \eta} t \quad (2)$$

Fibrous reinforcement is a porous material that can be idealized as a capillary tube network and capillary ascension is described in this case by the modified Washburn equation:

$$h^2(t) = \left[\frac{c\bar{r}}{2} \right] \frac{\gamma_L \cos \theta_a}{\eta} t \quad (3)$$

where \bar{r} is the mean capillary radius and c is a constant accounting for the tortuous path of liquid in the equivalent capillary tube arrangement (Fig.1-b). This parameter is inversely related to tortuosity, it increases when tortuosity decreases. This equation for a porous medium packed in a cylindrical sample holder, in the form of squared mass gain over time is:

$$m^2(t) = \left[\frac{(c\bar{r})^2 \varepsilon^2 (\pi R^2)^2}{2} \right] \frac{\rho^2 \gamma_L \cos \theta_a}{\eta} t \quad (4)$$

where ε is the relative porosity and R the inner radius of the sample holder. The term in the square brackets will be referred as C and defined as the geometric porous medium factor.

2.2 Darcy law

A flow through a porous medium is usually modelled with the well-known Darcy law [10], relating an equivalent fluid velocity v_D to the pressure drop, through the permeability of medium K and the liquid viscosity η :

$$v_D = -\frac{K}{\eta} \frac{dP}{dh} \quad (5)$$

This equation knowing the fiber volume ratio V_f , thus the porosity ε of medium, can be related to the distance $h(t)$ travelled by the flow front during filling:

$$\frac{h(t)}{t} = -\frac{K}{\varepsilon\eta} \frac{dP}{dh} \quad (6)$$

Introducing a negative capillary pressure P_{cap} in the pressure gradient (Fig.1-c) and integrating the precedent equation linearly, it is possible to obtain an expression of the squared wicking height over time, that is:

$$h^2(t) = \frac{2KP_{cap}}{\varepsilon\eta} t \quad (7)$$

If wicking occurs in a cylindrical sample holder with known dimensions, this equation in form of mass gain during filling of the medium becomes:

$$m^2(t) = \frac{2K\varepsilon\rho^2(\pi R^2)^2 P_{cap}}{\eta} t \quad (8)$$

Figure 1: Capillary ascension in: (a) a tube, (b) a porous medium according to modified Washburn equation, (c) a porous medium according to Darcy law.

2.3 Equivalence law for capillary pressure

In order to give a physical meaning to the capillary pressure $-P_{cap}$, it is thus possible to make the equivalence in mass gain of Washburn (Eq.4) and Darcy (Eq.8) equations. The resultant expression is:

$$P_{cap} = (c\bar{r})\varepsilon \frac{\gamma_L \cos \theta_a}{4K} \quad (9)$$

All parameters depending on the geometry of the sample holder and the fluid (viscosity and density) are simplified and the capillary pressure depends on morphology of the porous medium (tortuosity c , porosity ε , mean radius \bar{r} , saturated permeability K) and parameters taking into account interactions between the fluid and the medium (liquid surface tension γ_L and the mean advancing contact angle θ_a).

3 MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 Fibrous reinforcements

Carbon reinforcement used in the present study is a powdered quasi-unidirectional fabric with 3% in volume of glass tows in weft direction (Fig.2a). This material was provided by Hexcel and its commercial designation is 48580[®]. The areal weight is 541 g/m² and density is 1.8 g/cm³.

Quasi-unidirectional flax fabric (Fig.2b) was provided by Libeco (FLAXDRY UD 180[®]). The areal weight and the density are respectively 180 g/m² and 1.45 g/cm³. With these woven characteristics,

wicking test samples were prepared at the volume fiber ratio of 40%. It is well-known that natural flax fibers have a hydrophilic character that make reinforcements difficult to wet with mostly dispersive polymer resins. Then a thermal treatment, shown in precedent work that modifies chemical composition and wettability of fiber surface [11], was carried out on fabric (Fig.2c), to evaluate its influence on wicking.

Figure 2: Quasi-UD fabrics: (a) carbon; (b) flax; (c) treated flax.

Focusing on capillary pressure, values of permeability for carbon reinforcements in the three principal directions were considered from literature [12]. In the transverse direction K_z has been estimated to $3 \cdot 10^{-13} \text{ m}^2$ and for other directions an empirical relation considering that $K_x = 2K_y = 100K_z$ was used [12].

3.2 Test liquids

Liquids used in this study were chosen as a function of their polar and dispersive components. N-Hexane was chosen as totally wetting liquid for its lower surface tension and no polar component and water simply for convenience in order to set this new procedure (Tab.2).

	η (mPa s)	ρ (g/cm ³)	γ_c^p (mN/m)	γ_c^d (mN/m)	γ_c (mN/m)
<i>n-Hexane</i>	0.32	0.659	0.0	18.4	18.4
<i>Water</i>	1.00	0.998	51.0	21.8	72.8

Table 1: Test liquid properties at 20°C.

3.3 Wicking experiments on fabrics

A DCAT11 tensiometer (DataPhysics Instrument GmbH, Fildestardt) was used to perform wicking tests on fabrics. A scheme of instrumentation is illustrated in Fig. 2. This tensiometer is provided with an electronic microbalance (resolution of 10 μg) to which the tested solid is clamped. In this case the tested solid consists in a cylindrical sample holder (inner radius R of 6 mm and a minimal height H of 20 mm), as shown in Fig.2, in which fabrics were placed. A piston ensures the compaction of the fiber arrangements, and the global volume fiber ratio V_f , from which the relative porosity $\varepsilon = 1 - V_f$ can be calculated. The vessel with test liquid moves with a speed of 0.5 mm/s up to the detection of the holder and then the recording of experimental data of mass gain as function of time starts. All tests were carried out under standardized conditions.

Moreover, in order to suppress the interaction between reinforcements and the sample holder that have been found to be determinant for some directions, a thin filter paper has been added between the sample holder and the tested reinforcement, ensuring formation of a liquid film.

Figure 2: Tensiometer (left) and cylindrical sample holder (right).

Washburn equation (Eq.4) was adopted for this experimental procedure to determine the apparent wetting properties of the porous medium. More precisely, knowing the square mass variation over time $m^2(t)$, the so-called geometric porous medium factor C and the advancing contact angle θ_a can be estimated experimentally with two wicking tests: the first one for C calculation with n-Hexane, for which the contact angle will be assumed as 0° , and the second one for the contact angle calculation with another test liquid. It was decided to carry out these second tests with water.

It is obvious that to calculate parameters with Washburn relation (Eq.4), curves recorded by the tensiometer during capillary wicking have to be fit with a linear trend. It is also important to specify that each curve obtained have to be shifted to zero after subtraction of both weight of the external meniscus due to the sample holder and wicking in the sample holder with filter but without fabric.

Examples of Washburn linear fit on some experimental curves for carbon fabrics are shown in Fig.3.

Figure 3: Washburn fit of two experimental tests in x-direction with carbon fabric. Test liquids: n-Hexane (left), Water (right).

It is possible to observe from plots that with both n-Hexane and water a linear fit of experimental wicking is well achieved, making possible to set constant C and then calculate a mean advancing contact angle θ_a . All curves reach an asymptotic equilibrium that is given by the height of the sample itself. The equilibrium weight is due to the saturation of the porous medium by the test liquid. It is thus related to the fiber volume ratio and the sample holder inner volume. Since the saturation is not perfect, especially at the top of the sample, dispersion in equilibrium weight could appear.

Wicking experiments have been developed to allow measurements in the three main directions of all reinforcements:

- the first direction, that is along the fibres (the warp direction), referred to as x-direction flow;
- the second direction, that is perpendicular to the fibres in the reinforcement plane (the weft direction), referred to as y-direction flow;
- the third direction, that is transverse to the reinforcement plane, referred to as z-direction flow.

To set tests in the first (x) and in the second (y) directions, strips of fabric were opportunely cut and rolled to insert them into the cylindrical sample holder. Length of those strips was calculated to obtain a fibre volume fraction V_f of 40%. For the third (z) direction, plies of the cylindrical holder radius were cut with a carbide punch and stacked. The number of plies was determined in order to have the same targeted V_f . A scheme to simply illustrate fiber orientations in the three principal directions is shown in Fig.4.

Figure 4: Scheme of studied three principal directions of flow.

3.4 Swelling tests on single natural fibers

Natural fibers are well-known to be sensitive to water sorption. Swelling of fibers can affect the measurement of mass gain with tensiometer and this effect can make difficult measurements of capillary parameters. However, modifying wetting character of flax fibers through a thermal treatment might also have an effect on liquid sorption. For these reasons, water sorption tests were carried out on single untreated and treated flax fibers.

Experimental procedure used here is very similar to Nguyen et al. [14]. Single filaments of flax fibers were extracted from treated and untreated yarns in dry conditions and kept between two thin glass plates. A water drop was then instilled between plates and the liquid spreading along the fiber was observed with an optical microscope. Swelling of fibers was observed to be quick (over 5 seconds). Change in fiber diameter during sorption was measured through image analysis with ImageJ as shown in Fig. 5 and a swelling ratio R_{sw} was calculated as:

$$R_{sw} = \frac{D_f}{D_i} \quad (10)$$

where D_i is the measured fiber diameter in dry conditions and D_f the measured diameter after swelling.

Figure 5: Optical measurements on flax fiber diameter before and after water spreading.

4 RESULTS

4.1 Wicking in carbon fabrics and determination of equivalent capillary pressure

In order to determine capillary pressure P_{cap} with the Eq. 9, the geometric product ($c \bar{r}$) has to be estimated by fitting experimental curves of tensiometer with n-Hexane. Then five tests were carried out in the three main directions of carbon reinforcements. As shown in Fig. 6 linear trend with the totally wetting liquid was found in all cases, allowing determination of porous geometric factor C and thus of the geometric product ($c \bar{r}$) for the three directions.

Figure 6: Washburn curves to determine geometric factor in the three main directions of the carbon fabric reinforcement.

Table 2 presents the means results of geometric constants showing that values in each direction are very different. The one estimated in the x-direction is higher than the one in the z-direction and the lowest is in the y-direction. Assuming a quasi-equivalent mean capillary radius, values of the geometric product should be the highest along fibers (x-direction) and the lowest in the y-direction (the tortuosity should be lower in z-direction due to the inter-tow channels). It is thus possible to validate the progression of results on geometric products with the morphology of the fibrous preform.

Similar tests (five for each direction) were carried out with water, in order to determine an apparent advancing contact angle θ_a , with the help of constant C determined earlier, and to use it later to estimate the capillary pressure (Eq.9). Fig.7 shows experimental curves that were fitted and Table 2 illustrates average results of calculated advancing contact angles for each direction. Even if wicking is faster in x-direction, calculation of contact angle depends on geometric constants and the lowest value of advancing contact angle was found in x-direction.

Figure 7: Washburn curves to determine advancing contact angles in the three main directions of the carbon fabric reinforcement.

Once that both geometric constants and wetting parameters are known, capillary pressure P_{cap} can be determined by means of Eq. 9 in each direction. Table 2 shows results that are relevant with ones found in literature: Values given by Verrey et al. [3] are 4 kPa for stitched non-crimp carbon

reinforcement oriented at $\pm 45^\circ$. Those values, measured in the plane of the reinforcement, are relevant with the present ones.

	C (mm^5)	$c \bar{r}$ (μm)	θ_a ($^\circ$)	P_{cap} (kPa)
<i>x-direction</i>	27.9 ± 3.4	12.1 ± 1.5	74.8 ± 2.3	1.15 ± 0.30
<i>y-direction</i>	4.0 ± 0.4	1.7 ± 0.2	65.3 ± 3.2	0.51 ± 0.14
<i>z-direction</i>	11.5 ± 2.4	4.9 ± 1.1	79.8 ± 1.6	32.10 ± 11.60

Table 2: Average results of wicking parameters and equivalent P_{cap} in three main directions.

There is a large difference between the capillary pressure in transverse direction and the other components. This is due to the lower permeability in transverse direction. This is also consistent with the fact that capillary effects are more important than viscous effects in porous media with low permeability.

4.2 Wicking in flax fabrics and swelling of single fibers

As for carbon fabrics, wicking tests for untreated and treated flax reinforcements were carried out. Fig. 8 (left) shows experimental curves obtained on five tests in x-direction for n-Hexane. A linear trend was observed for both treated and untreated flax fabrics, allowing determination of geometric factors (Tab.3). These values in x-direction are in the same order than the ones found for carbon fabric. A slight difference is observed for treated flax reinforcement indicating probably a decrease of tortuosity by treatment (modification of the diameter).

Figure 8: Washburn curves to determine geometric (left) and capillary parameters (right) in x-direction of flax reinforcements.

A more relevant influence of treatment on flax reinforcement can be observed in Fig. 8 (right), where it is obvious to observe that linear fit of Washburn equation is possible on treated fabrics, while untreated ones show a different trend. It is thus possible to calculate with Eq.9 an equivalent capillary pressure only for treated fabrics. Differences in wicking are probably due to sensitivity to water that induces swelling in flax fibers. Swelling in natural fibers during wicking causes an increase of fiber volume ratio, involving to reach more slowly the equilibrium weight that is also observed to be smaller. Capillary rise was already found to be faster for treated yarns and chopped fibers, thus this result is coherent [11].

	C (mm^5)	$c \bar{r}$ (μm)
<i>Untreated Flax</i>	28.1 ± 3.2	12.2 ± 1.4
<i>Treated Flax</i>	35.1 ± 2.8	15.3 ± 1.3

Table 3: Average results of geometric factors in x-direction.

To evaluate sensitivity to water sorption, fifteen tests of swelling were carried out on treated and untreated single fibers as described in paragraph 3.4. Flax fibers show a large dispersion in terms of

diameter and the diameter is variable also along the fiber. For this reason three measures of diameter were carried out on the same fiber in dry and wet conditions (Fig. 5) and for each fiber the swelling ratio was calculated (Eq. 10). Fig.6 shows results of swelling tests with water for untreated and treated fibers. The large variability of diameter and the large dispersion in swelling ratio, can be clearly observed in Fig. 9. However comparison between the two graphs in Fig. 9 shows that the treatment does not affect significantly morphology of fibers (mean dry diameter of untreated flax was found $16,8 \pm 4.7 \mu\text{m}$, $17,5 \pm 5.9 \mu\text{m}$ for the treated ones). This is consistent with results of wicking with n-Hexane. Moreover swelling of fibers and its dispersion is lower for treated fibers (mean swelling ratio of untreated is 1.27 ± 0.13 vs. 1.11 ± 0.07 of treated). Treatment makes fibers less sensitive to water sorption and this can thus explain differences of wicking in untreated and treated fabrics.

Figure 9: Results of swelling ratio as function of initial dry diameter for untreated (left) and treated (right) flax fibers.

5 CONCLUSIONS

In this work a new expression of capillary pressure through the equivalence between Washburn and Darcy laws was proposed. This physical parameter has to be taken into account during impregnation of preforms by LCM processes. Capillary pressure depends on morphology of reinforcement (primary fiber orientation) and capillary parameters considering interactions between the fluid and the porous medium. In order to identify those factors, wicking tests were performed on quasi-UD carbon and flax fabrics evaluating liquid flow in the three main directions of reinforcements. Linear trend found for carbon fabrics allows to fit experimental curves by Washburn equation and then to identify values of capillary pressure for each direction. Moisture sorption affects wicking kinetics in flax reinforcements because of fibers swelling. A thermal treatment was carried out on fibers in order to minimize this effect and indeed swelling tests proved that it was effective. Experimental wicking tests on treated reinforcements show then a linear trend (considering the square of mass against time), similar to those obtained with carbon reinforcements.

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